

Fanyin

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Entry tags: Excavated text, Text, a hybrid of popular beliefs, Early Chinese text, Peking University Bamboo Texts, Religious Group, Early Chinese Traditions

The Fan yin 反淫 (“Against Excesses”) belongs to a collection of Han-dynasty bamboo-slip manuscripts donated by an anonymous alumnus to Peking University in 2009 (Beijing daxue chutu wenxian yanjiusuo 2011: 49); its provenance is unknown. Experts at the university dated it to the period between the reigns of Emperor Wu 武 (r. 141-87 BCE) and Emperor Xuan 宣 (r. 74-49/48 BCE) [Beijing daxue chutu wenxian yanjiusuo 2011: 50]. The editors of the Fan yin think it was composed in the early Western Han period (which began in 206 BCE) based on its literary diction and calligraphic style. The Fan yin contains 1,225 graphs on fifty-nine slips with thirty-five of them intact without damage. On the back of its first slip (inventory number 2589) were written two graphs—“fan yin”—which do not appear together in the text itself; they are thus taken to be its original title. Written in the form of rhymed rhapsody (fu 賦), the Fan yin presents an imaginary conversation between Hun 魂 (“ethereal soul”) who plays the physician and an ailing Pozi 魄子 (“corporeal soul”) in need of treatment, apparently due to his excessive indulgences, a condition indicated by the word yin (excesses) in the text’s title. In early China, it was widely believed that human beings were each endowed with a dual soul comprised of hun and po. This was probably the result of a fusion of soul beliefs in North and South China in the sixth century BCE. While po functions as the life principle of human beings which determines the life and death of a person, “hun is the seat of human emotions, feelings and sentiments as well as the center for willing—it is, in effect, an aggregate of psychological attributes in man. Such conception continued into the Han dynasty (Lo 2008: 26, 33). Yet, it was probably unprecedented when hun and po were turned into fictional characters in an imaginary dialogue some four hundred years later. In the Huainanzi 淮南子, a text of eclectic philosophy attributed to Prince Huainan (179 BCE-122 BCE), there was an exchange between the two souls on how to attain the Dao 道, where Po seeks counsel from Hun who has embodied it (He 1989: 1101-1102). Given its similar literary device, it is possible that the Fan yin might be written around the same time as well. As the opening of the text is missing, it is not clear if Pozi initially seeks treatment for his malady from Hun but after eleven ineffective attempts to lure Pozi with the extraordinary sensual pleasures of various sorts, Hun recommends him to invite friends and people who admire his “lofty aspirations” (高義) to play games and have fun together in his expansive and luxurious quarters. To this, Pozi is willing enough to oblige. But seeing his positive response, Hun goes one step further to entice him with a proposed gathering with learned men from all under Heaven such as esteemed statesmen (Su Qin 蘇秦 and Zhang Yi 張儀), respected philosophers (Mencius 孟子, Mozi 墨子, Yang Zhu 楊朱) and accomplished poets (Song Yu 宋玉, Qu Yuan 屈原 and Jing Cuo 景差) from Warring States times which ended in 221 BCE. The purpose is to “examine with them the successes and failures of declining ages, discuss the subtleties of all under Heaven, and putting in order the this and that of the myriad things” (巧【=考】諸衰世之成敗，論天下之精微，理萬物之是非) with Confucius and Laozi as arbitrators in the audience (孔老監聽). Pozi’s interest is piqued indeed, yet an anti-climax is introduced when Hun decides on a still better therapy of roaming in the higher realm of “utmost purity” (至清), casting off the filthy bodily shell (蟬說【=蛻】濁穢【=穢】) in the process of spiritual transformation while “dwelling in the palace of leisure and quietude and attending court with the leather cap” (處閒靜之宮，冠弁以聽朝). The precondition for Pozi to attain such liberation is to remain “empty-minded, tranquil, serene, and relaxed” (虛靜恬愉). To do so, he must practice what Hun calls “engaging in the affairs of non-action and performing the teaching without words” (處無為之事，行不言之教)—a direct quotation from the Laozi. No sooner has Pozi heard the suggestion than he perspires profusely and recovers from his illness. Despite its obvious Daoist flavor, the philosophical and medical underpinnings of the Fan yin are rich, and meticulous analysis will reveal the interplay of Warring States thought and medicine in early Han times. More ostensibly, the Fan yin shows a striking resemblance to the

Seven Stimuli (Qi fa 七發), a famous and influential rhymed rhapsody attributed to the scholar-official cum poet Mei Sheng 枚乘 (d. ca. 141 BCE) [Fu 2015: 144-150; Knechtges 2010: 665]. The Qi fa, structured in the format of a dialogue in which a persuader volunteers to offer advice to heal Prince of Chu who becomes bedridden with sensual excesses. He adopts a strategy similar to Hun's in the Fan yin, trying to seduce the ailing prince, step by step, with further indulgence in rapturous music, lavish food and drink, sumptuous banquets, exciting hunting, and delightful wave-watching. Likewise he fails. It is only when he proposes to the prince to have an audience with fangshi 方士 magicians to “discuss the subtleties of all under Heaven, and putting in order the this and that of the myriad things” does he finally succeed. Upon hearing his suggestion, the prince sweats copiously and recuperates himself without actually listening to the “essential words and wonderful teachings” (要言妙道) promised with said meeting. Not only is the proposed activity identical to what Hun recommends to Pozi, but so is its immediate effect on the prince as well. The relationship between the Fan Yin and Qi fa deserves critical investigation and will shed light on the early history of rhymed rhapsody. Fu Gang 傅剛 argues that the Fan yin was an earlier work by Mei Sheng which functioned as a draft for the eventual product of Qi fa (Fu 2015: 171) but this is far from being conclusive.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 100 BCE

Region: Chang'an (長安)

Region tags: China, Shaanxi Province 陝西省, Xi'an 西安

Chang'an, in present-day Xi'an, was the capital of the Western Han dynasty.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Beijing Daxue chutu wenxian yanjiusuo 北京大學出圖文獻研究所 ed. Western Han Bamboo Slips Text in the Collection of Peking University 北京大學藏西漢竹書, vol. 4 Shanghai: Shanghai Guji chubanshe, 2015.
- Source 2: Fu Gang 傅剛. “A Brief Introduction of the Han Bamboo Slip Text, “Fanyin”, in the Collection of Peking University” 北京大學藏漢簡《反淫》簡說, in Beijing Daxue chutu wenxian yanjiusuo ed., Beijing Daxue cang Xi Han zhushu 北京大學藏西漢竹簡 (Shanghai: Shanghai Guji chubanshe, 2015), Vol. 4, pp.163-64.
- Source 3: Knechtges David R.. “A Newly Discovered Han Fu: The Peking University Bamboo Strip Manuscript of the ‘Fan yin’ 反淫 (Contra Immoderation),” manuscript, 2017.

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- Source 1: Zheng Banghong 鄭邦宏. “Beida Hanjian ‘Wang ji’ ‘Fan Yin’ de ezi zhengli” 北大漢簡《妄稽》《反淫》訛字整理, Chutu wenxian 出土文獻 10 (2017): 201-205.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Fudan Daxue Chutu Wenxian yu Guwenzi yanjiu zhongxin wang 復旦大學出土文獻與古文字研究中心網, <http://www.gwz.fudan.edu.cn/Web/Show/2850>
- Source 1 Description: Chen Jian 陳劍. “Wangji’ ‘Fanyin’ jiaozi shiyi” 《妄稽》《反淫》校字拾遺

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: No online corpora is available at this time.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The "Fanyin" was part of a collection of bamboo texts bought from Hong Kong in 2009. Its provenance is not known.

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– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Field doesn't know

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Notes: The text does not talk about the mind per se.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Notes: The text was not about a debate over mind-body dualism.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is clear from the text that excesses of sensual pleasures were inadvisable as they were harmful to physical and mental health.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - No
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - No
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - No
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
 - Notes: Avoid the excesses of sensual pleasures.

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - No

- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - No
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes
 - Notes: spiritual transcendence

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

- ↳ Monogamy (males)
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Monogamy (females)
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males)
 - Yes

Notes: Although sexual constraints were not explicitly mentioned in the text, its warning against the excess of sensual pleasures no doubt would include them.

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females)
 - Yes

Notes: Although the protagonist in the text was apparently male, its warning against excessive sensual pleasures would be equally applicable to women at the time.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: The remedy to the patient's sickness is the aspiration to spiritual wandering in a realm where the healed patient, transcending above the rise and fall of human history and petty philosophical debates, delights in tranquility and peace. The goal of recovery goes beyond ethics.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

Notes: The imaginary dialogue between the ethereal soul and the corporeal soul was intended to be creative and entertaining.

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The Western Han empire (202 BCE - 9 CE).

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text was probably written by a single author.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The Fan yin no longer survives in its entirety presumably due to natural deterioration but it should be intact when it was entombed, so it was not destroyed by suppression of any kind. As the bamboo text was not archaeologically excavated, it might have suffered some damage before it finally found its home in Peking University.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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